

Situation 2: Schools closed

Use the/the buttons to select your options

Order

Compare

Opening of primary schools at
100% capacity

Opening of primary schools in a
hybrid manner

Opening of secondary schools at
100% capacity

Opening of secondary schools in
a hybrid manner

3rd dose required for teachers

Quarantine for suspected and
confirmed cases of COVID-19

Other effects

Health effects on parents and teachers
(number of weekly COVID-19 infections per
1000 inhabitants)

5

Primary school students with emotional
problems for every 10 students

3

Secondary school students with emotional
problems for every 10 students

3

There are approximately 3.8 million
primary school students and 2.7 million
secondary school students. The learning
loss in months for each student would be:

9